

TANGENT

PROJECT MANAGEMENT HANDBOOK. THIRD RELEASE.

D9.6.

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Executive summary

This deliverable, “D9.6. Project management handbook. Third release.”, intends to gather the different updates on management made, since D9.1. (M2, November 2021) and D9.5 (M18, February 2023) were delivered.

This report covers the changes in managerial aspects related to project structure, consortium coordination procedures, quality and risk management, project reporting, document management, decision-making and conflict resolution and payment procedures. Moreover, the amendment (AMD-955273-22) to the TANGENT project is introduced in separate sections.

Key words

Project management, H2020, project reporting, management procedures.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
PMH	Project Management Handbook
N/A	Not applicable
WP	Work package
WPL	Work package leader
EC	European Commission
PMB	Project Management Board
PTC	Project Technical Committee
IEB	Innovation & Exploitation Board

1 Introduction

The Project Management Handbook (PMH) covers aspects related to the project's organization, procedures, and quality assurance procedures. The PMH provides useful information to all partners about the procedures that will be followed during the project execution for communication and reporting purposes.

This deliverable covers the different updates on management during the second period of the project (M19-M39). Hence, this report reviews each of the sections contained in "D9.1 Project Management Handbook. First Release" (M2) and "D9.5 Project Management Handbook. Second Release" identifying the changes during the project time between M18 to M39, covering:

- Project management structure
- Internal coordination procedures
- Quality and risk management
- Project reporting
- Document management
- Decision-making process and conflict resolution
- Payment procedures

Furthermore, the information about the project amendment (AMD-955273-22) is presented in the Section 8 of this report.

2 Project management structure

The Project management board (PMB), Project Technical Committee (PTC), Innovation & Exploitation Board (IEB) and the TANGENT Forum are the TANGENT boards presented in D9.1.

Along the second period of the project new appointments have been performed to the boards by the partners: **A-to-Be**, **RUPPRECHT**, **POLIS** and **CEFRIEL**. The updates are shown in the Table 1:

No	Organisation name	PMB	PTC	IEB
1	DEUSTO	Leire Serrano	Antonio Masegosa	Leire Serrano
2	AIMSUN	Athina Tympakianaki	N/A	Athina Tympakianaki
3	NTUA	Eleni Vlahogianni	Eleni Vlahogianni	Eleni Vlahogianni
4	IMEC	Ynte Vanderhoydonc	Mohammadmahdi Rahimiasl	Siegfried Mercelis
5	CEFRIEL	Marco Comerio	Mario Scrocca (replacing Marco Comerio)	Marco Comerio
6	RUPPRECHT	Wolfgang Backhaus	Lakshya Pandit (replacing Morgane Juliat)	Wolfgang Backhaus
7	ID4MOBILITY	Véronique Rottier	Véronique Rottier	Lucie Tristant
8	RENNES	Céline Quéron	N/A	Céline Quéron
9	A-to-Be	Lara Moura (Feb-Dec 2023) Daniel Matos (Dec 2023 -Jun 2024) Frederico Vaz (Jun 2024 - present)	Tiago Dias	Lara Moura (Feb-Dec 2023) Daniel Matos (Dec 2023 -Jun 2024) Frederico Vaz (Jun 2024 - present)
10	CARRIS	Joao Vieira	N/A	Joao Vieira
11	TFGM	Hannah Tune	N/A	Hannah Tune
12	PANTEIA	Arnaud Burgess	N/A	Geert Koops
13	POLIS	Mark Meyer	Mark Meyer (replacing Suzanne Hoadley)	Juliette Thijs

Table 1: Updates on the nomination to board during the second period

Additionally, the partner ID4CAR modified the official short name to ID4MOBILITY.

3 Internal coordination procedures

The internal coordination procedures, including monitoring project progress, using established information and communication tools, scheduling meetings, and reporting, as outlined in Deliverable 9.1, has remained unchanged during the second period of the TANGENT project.

4 Quality and risk management

The quality check of the deliverables review process remains unchanged from the previous reporting period. Specifically, Deliverable D9.1 outlines the quality check process for project deliverables, including stages, responsible partners, and timelines. The timelines for each phase were updated in Deliverable D9.5 to enhance the quality check process. Moreover, the internal review process has also remained consistent.

5 Project reporting

The consortium follows the deliverable submission procedure established in D9.1. Since then, there have not been any changes in this regard.

The semi-annually routine of internal progress report submitted by each project partners has remained consistent as well.

For the Final report, consortium will apply the template for reporting financial aspects presented in Annex I of the D9.5. The technical report will be formatted according to the template provided by the EC.

6 Document management

The consortium applies the document management presented in D9.1 and D9.5 without modifications.

7 Decision-making process and conflict resolution

The procedure of the decision-making and conflict resolution including the voting rules and the escalation process for technical issues resolution remains the same as it is described in the D9.1 and D9.5

8 Amendment request to the Grant Agreement

TANGENT consortium decided to request an amendment for a project extension of 3 months and for removing the linked third party EEGLE. The amendment was submitted the 4th of August 2024 by Deusto, and was accepted by the EC on the 15th of August 2024.

The amendment includes the following aspects:

1. The linked third party 7.2 EEGLE (linked to beneficiary 7- ID4MOBILITY) terminate their participation in TANGENT due to compulsory liquidation. The pending activities of “Task 7.2 Operation of the tests: testing of the subsystems” and “Task 7.3 Upscaling and full operation: testing of the overall system” has been assigned to beneficiary ID4MOBILITY. EEGLE pending budget (27.000 EUR) were transferred to beneficiary ID4MOBILITY.
2. The TANGENT project has been granted by an extension of 3 months in order to finalise the developments (WP2, 4, 5, 6) and execute the relevant testing activities (WP7). Moreover, project extension has affected consequentially the WP1 and WP8, which are devoted to the multi-actor coordination models & policies and dissemination & exploitation actions. Therefore, the project end date is November 30, 2024, instead of August 31, 2024.

The due date of different milestones has been updated (Table 2: Updates on the milestones’ deadlines):

Milestone	Title	Due date according the GA	Modified due date
MS4	Final release of subsystems ready: API for data harmonisation and fusion; travel behaviour models; transport prediction models; Optimization models for transport network management. First release of the TANGENT tool integrated.	M28	M32 (Apr 2024)
MS5	Final release of the TANGENT tool integrated	M33	M37 (Sep 2024)
MS6	TANGENT tool tested and validated	M36	M39 (Nov 2024)

Table 2: Updates on the milestones’ deadlines

The modification of due dates of the deliverables is presented in the Table 3: Updates on the deliverables

Deliverable	Title	Due date according the GA	Modified due date
D1.5.	Report on TANGENT Forum activities.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D1.6.	Multi-actor cooperation models for NTM. Second release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M39 (Nov 2024)

Deliverable	Title	Due date according the GA	Modified due date
D1.7.	Policy, regulatory and planning framework for TNM. Second release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D6.5	TANGENT tool development and integration. Second release.	M33 (May 2024)	M37 (Sep 2024)
D6.6	Smart infrastructure index report. Second release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D7.3.	Assessment of the testing results in the Case Study of Rennes.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D7.4.	Assessment of the testing results in the Case Study of Lisbon.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D7.5.	Assessment of the testing results in the Case Study of Greater Manchester.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D7.6.	Assessment of the testing results in the Case Study of Athens.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M39 (Nov 2024)
D7.7.	Impact assessment report.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M39 (Nov 2024)
D8.4.	Final booklet.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D8.5.	Policy recommendations.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M39 (Nov 2024)
D8.5.	Exploitation and business model plan.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D8.5.	Report on dissemination activities (including cooperation with other projects). Second release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D9.6.	Project management handbook. Third release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D9.8.	Data Management Plan. Third release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D9.9.	IPR management and Data Protection. Second release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)
D9.10.	Ethics monitoring. Second release.	M36 (Aug 2024)	M38 (Oct 2024)

Table 3: Updates on the deliverables

The updated Gantt submitted during the amendment process is presented in the Annex I.

3. The DoA of the Grant Agreement was updated according to the requested changes.

9 Payment procedures

So far, Deusto as project coordinator has received the pre-financing and interim payment from the EC and has distributed among the partners. The distribution of Interim payment among partners was executed in September 2023, as presented in the Table 4:

Partner name	Interim payment
DEUSTO	82.252,50 €
AIMSUN	43.375,00 €
NTUA	55.850,00 €
IMEC	41.922,88 €
CEFRIEL	41.062,50 €
RUPPRECHT	36.625,00 €
ID4CAR	48.625,00 €
RENNES	6.937,50 €
A-TO-BE	55.859,38 €
CARRIS	14.750,00 €
TFGM	16.087,63 €
PANTEIA	18.012,50 €
POLIS	23.575,00 €
Total	484.934,88 €

Table 4: Distribution of interim payment

10 Conclusions

The nature of the PMH is a “live” document, therefore, the third release presents the updates and modifications on management aspects from the first (D9.1) and second (D9.5) versions of the document.

The present deliverable reviews all the contents in original Project Management Plan (D9.1) and its second release (D9.5), and details updates since then, specifically on:

- Project management structure: new appointments on the representatives of the boards are included.
- Payment procedures: the status of payments is detailed.
- The Amendment performed: updated the duration of the project, new dates of submission of the milestones and deliverables, withdraw of the EEGLE as a linked third party, and their pending budget accordingly.

11 References

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